

ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY**Usmonov Toxir Zokirjanovich**

Basic doctoral student of the Department of Economics of Namangan Engineering and Technology Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6792029>

Abstract. *The transformation of the socio-economic system under the influence of the introduction of ICT in various fields of activity leads to the formation and development of the digital economy. Under these conditions, there is a complication of the forms of organization of economic activity, new prospects for the development of economic entities appear. The authors of the article note that digital technologies, their use and production are the sources of development of modern small business.*

Keywords: *small business, digital economy, digital technologies, digitalization*

ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА В ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ

Аннотация. *Трансформация социально-экономической системы под влиянием внедрения ИКТ в различные сферы деятельности приводит к формированию и развитию цифровой экономики. В этих условиях происходит усложнение форм организации экономической деятельности, появляются новые перспективы развития хозяйствующих субъектов. Авторы статьи отмечают, что цифровые технологии, их использование и производство являются источниками развития современного малого бизнеса.*

Ключевые слова: *малый бизнес, цифровая экономика, цифровые технологии, цифровизация.*

INTRODUCTION

The revolutionary shifts that have taken place in such areas as information technology, robotics, microelectronics, telecommunications have given rise to a relatively new and important phenomenon - the digital economy (digital economy). The generally accepted understanding of the digital economy is associated with the analysis of economic activities based on digital technologies, in which digital (electronic) data arrays are the key production factor.

Recently, the digital economy has been a priority area in various countries, as evidenced by the presence of government programs and strategies aimed at developing and stimulating digital technologies. Only in the countries of the European Union (EU), according to the European Commission, in 2017 there were more than 30 national and regional programs for the digitalization of the economy (on digitizing industry). Russia has also adopted and is implementing the national program “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation”, which involves the digitalization of the Russian economy in various areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As the demand for digital technologies continues to grow, every industry in the country must adapt to the digital economy. From this point of view, there is a need to improve small business in the digital economy; many scientists have theoretical views on this. Including:

A theoretical analysis of the digitalization of the economy allows us to highlight the following aspects of this problem:

1) search for new opportunities for more effective interaction of already functioning enterprises with customers, partners, suppliers and other interested parties based on the use of digital technologies;

2) definition of new areas of activity of business entities. The solution of these issues is relevant for small businesses, since, being an important element in the structure of any economy, it performs important socio-economic functions.

Traditionally occupying leading positions in the service sector, small businesses serve as a platform for introducing innovations in various fields of activity. Therefore, the use of digital technologies, mobile Internet can be a source of modern small business development.

The study used economic, comparative, analytical and sample observation, statistical and forecasting and other methods.

RESULTS

The relevance of the problem of the development of the digital economy and the introduction of technologies remains actively discussed, since a unified theoretical and methodological basis for research in this area is only being formed and has not been fully developed, which gives impetus to its in-depth analysis and study. Often, the definition of the digital economy is replaced by a listing of the directions of its influence on the economy and the social sphere.

Involving small businesses in the digital economy is possible in the following ways (Figure 1):

- digitalization of small business based on the use of information and communication technologies, which leads to the formation of new business models;
- production of digital technologies by small businesses;
- as a result of the development and implementation of state programs for the digitalization of small businesses.

Figure 1. The process of involving small businesses in the digital economy

Initially, the introduction of digital technologies was a priority for large and medium-sized enterprises, since it required significant investments. However, at present, one can observe the introduction of modern information and communication technologies by small businesses, which ensures an increase in efficiency, opens up access to new markets, and makes it possible to realize the full potential of innovation.

In their activities, small businesses use various digital technologies that can reduce the costs of doing business: financial instruments of online payments; targeted advertising tools in social networks, accounting programs, CRM systems, etc.

The most common tools for the use of digital technologies by small businesses include:

- customer relationship management (CRM) - systems for customer relationship management;
- enterprise resource planning (ERP) - enterprise resource management (the concept of resources includes: materials, equipment, labor resources, etc.). ERP systems provide control, manageability and transparency of financial, personnel and inventory flows in the company;
- cloud computing service - used to perform complex calculations, exchange information, store data, gain access to artificial intelligence capabilities, etc. Cloud solutions provide cross-functional transparency and data consistency, speed up the process of updating information platforms with minimal or no cost, reduce operating costs and guarantee security of sensitive client data and internal data.

DISCUSSION

It should be noted that the current development of digital technologies is complex and finds its expression in new synergistic forms, for example, the local ERP system is replaced by a new cloud system, which allows employees and management to receive in real time the information necessary for doing business, the most efficient and effective customer service.

The use of various digital technologies in general increases the efficiency of activities, and, consequently, the competitiveness of enterprises. For example, such successful startups as Air B&B, Uber, which are advertising platforms, enable small businesses to convey information about their services to the widest range of customers. Of course, there are no single algorithms for the use of digital technologies by small businesses that lead to increased efficiency and lower costs. Without significant funds, the digital transformation of small businesses can begin with the modernization of IT infrastructure, increasing information mobility, using technologies for real-time analytics and working with big data.

Another way to digitalize small businesses and involve them in the digital economy is to produce digital products and sell them on the market. Small business, innovative in its essence, can actively participate in the production of the following innovative digital technologies:

- wireless communication technologies: development of IT devices and applications, development of various applications for smartphones and other devices;
- virtual and augmented reality technologies: development of software for virtual and augmented reality, development and production of devices for interaction with virtual and augmented reality (glasses, helmets, etc.);
- development and production of chips, sensors, processors necessary for the development of digital technologies;
- development of new robotic and sensor systems for industrial applications;

- design and engineering of products for the digital space;
- development of new directions for the application of artificial intelligence; □development of software for quantum systems;
- digital design and construction, etc.

The process of active involvement of small businesses in the digital economy is possible through participation in pilot projects that are aimed at identifying effective approaches to the introduction of digital technologies in various industries and allow obtaining up-to-date information from both companies and customers. The positive experience of such practice is already known.

CONCLUSIONS

The digitalization of the economy opens up new opportunities and prospects for small businesses. The use of digital technologies allows small businesses to reduce costs, increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise, launch new types of products, occupying certain niches in the market of digital goods and services. Along with the emerging prospects, there are also new problems associated not only with the search for investments, but also with the formation of new competencies of small businesses that allow them to successfully navigate in the conditions of digital transformation. In addition, the use of digital technologies leads to increased competition not only from domestic but also foreign market participants.

Reference

1. Digital Economy Report 2019. Creating Value and Benefits for Developing Countries - Geneva, UN. [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://unctad.org>.
2. Rasskazova NV Economic interests of small business and the problem of sustainable development of the socio-economic system // Journal of economic theory. - 2009. - No. 3. - p. 226-230.
3. Digital economy. / short statistical collection / G.I. Abdrakhmanova , K.O. Vishnevsky, L.M. Gohberg and others; National research . University "Higher School of Economics". - M.: NRU HSE, 2020. - 112 p.
4. Granata G. Predicting Trends and Building Strategies for Consumer Engagement in Retail Environments. / G. Granata ,, A. Moretta Tartaglione , T. Tsiakis, Hershey ,. - PA: IGI Global, 2019. - 1-413 p.
5. Mukhitdinov, S. Z. (2021). COVID-19 PANDEMIA IN UZBEKISTAN AGRICULTURE AND ITS IMPACT ON THE SUPPLY CHAIN. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 2(01), 177-183.
6. Мухитдинов, Ш. З. (2021). ТАДБИРКОРЛИК СУБЪЕКТЛАРИДА ХАТАРЛАРНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ-УСЛУБИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 939-943.
7. Akhadova K. S. PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE ENGINEERS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 316-323.
8. Ахадова К. С. О ГРУППЕ ИЗОМЕТРИЙ СЛОЕНОГО МНОГООБРАЗИЯ //Естественные и технические науки. – 2014. – №. 1. – С. 14-17.

9. Axadova K.S. BO'LAJAK MUHANDISLARNING MATEMATIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALALARI//NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi. -2022. -№3. - C. 703-707.
10. Axadova K.S. TEXNIKA OLIY O'QUV YURTLARIDA TALABALARNING MATEMATIK KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI//NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi. -2021. -№12. - C. 507-512.